

Studies in the Synthesis of Coumarin Dimers Part I: Synthesis of Bicoumarinoxy Methanes

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The presence of coumarin-type compounds in plants has been well established. Coumarin dimers were first shown to occur naturally when Link¹ reported the structure of 3,3'-methylene bis(4-hydroxycoumarin), (dicoumarol) as two coumarins connected by a methylene group. A different type of coumarin dimer was reported by Tschesche and coworkers². They identified daphnoretin³ as two coumarins linked by an ether bridge. Mihashi and co-workers^{4,5} have recently isolated a third type of coumarin dimer in which the two coumarins are linked through a carbon carbon bond. They named their compound Matsukaze-lactone.

Synthetic compounds of the latter structure are known and are called bicoumarinyls. Grover, Jain and Seshadri⁶ studied the methylenation of hydroxy flavonoids and resorcinol derivatives and synthesised different biflavonyls of novel type. Methylenation may be regarded as a common natural process. In the group of plant phenolics, methylenation of a catechol unit is often encountered particularly in lignans, alkaloids and some flavonoids.

The present work was carried out with a view to study the methylenation of different hydroxy coumarins. Methylenation was carried out by refluxing the mixture of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin, anhydrous potassium carbonate, dry acetone and methylene iodide where bimolecular compound linked by a methylenedioxy group in the reactive 7-position was obtained. The compound was assigned the structure bi(4-methyl-7-coumarinoxy)methane (I).

(I)

1. M. A. Stalman, C. F. Huebner and K. P. Link, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1941, **138**, 513
2. R. Tschesche, U. Schacht, G. Legler and Liebigs, *Ann. Chem.*, 1963, **662**, 113.
3. A. L. Livingston, E. M. Bickoff, and L. J. Jurd, *Agr. Food Chem.*, 1964, **12**, 535.
5. T. Miyazaki and S. Mihashi, *Chem. Pharm. Bull. (Tokyo)*, 1964, **12**, 1232.
5. T. Miyazaki, S. Mihashi and K. Okabayashi, *ibid.*, 1964, **12**, 1236.
6. S. K. Grover, A. C. Jain and T. R. Seshadri, *Tetrahedron*, 1964, **20**, 555.

In a similar manner bi(7-coumarinoxy); bi(3-coumarinoxy), bi(4-coumarinoxy); bi(4-methyl-5-coumarinoxy); bi(4-methyl-6-coumarinoxy); bi(4,7-dimethyl-5-coumarinoxy); bi(4-phenyl-7-coumarinoxy) methane were synthesised from 7-hydroxy-; 3-hydroxy-; 4-hydroxy-; 5-hydroxy-4-methyl-; 6-hydroxy-4-methyl-; 5-hydroxy-4,7-dimethyl-; 7-hydroxy-4-phenylcoumarin.

All these compounds gave a positive gallic acid-sulphuric acid test⁷, thus indicating the presence of methylene dioxy group.

EXPERIMENTAL*

The methylene dioxy test was performed by heating the compound with gallic acid and con. sulphuric acid on a boiling water bath; emerald green colour was taken as a positive reaction.

TABLE I

Bi(Coumarinoxy) methane derivatives

Hydroxy coumarins (g) 1	bi-(coumarinoxy) methane derivative (g) 2	Refluxing time (hrs) 3	Crystallising solvent and nature of the crystals ^a 4	M.P. °C 5	Molecular formula 6	Carbon		Hydrogen	
						Found % 7	reqd. % 8	Found % 9	reqd. % 10
7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-coumarin (2.0).	bi-(4-methyl-7-coumarinoxy) methane (0.3).	4	Acetic acid shining needles.	224	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₆	69.67	69.22	4.47	4.43
7-Hydroxy-coumarin (2.0).	bi(7-coumarinoxy) methane (0.5).	8	Acetic acid colourless crystals.	260	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ O ₆	67.69	67.85	3.78	3.60
3-Hydroxy-coumarin (1.5).	bi(3-coumarinoxy) methane (0.05).	15	Acetic acid white crystals.	259	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ O ₆	67.47	67.85	3.19	3.60
4-Hydroxy-coumarin (1.0).	bi(4-coumarinoxy) methane (0.1).	35	Acetic acid yellow shining needles.	255	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ O ₆	67.38	67.85	3.37	3.60
5-Hydroxy-4-methyl coumarin (0.5).	bi(4-methyl-5-coumarinoxy) methane (0.3).	15	Acetic acid shining needles.	238	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₆	68.81	69.22	4.08	4.43
6-Hydroxy-4-methyl coumarin (1.0).	bi(4-methyl-6-coumarinoxy) methane (0.2).	8	Acetic acid shining plates.	212	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₆	69.18	69.22	4.44	4.43
7-Hydroxy-4-phenyl coumarin (2.0).	bi(4-phenyl-7-coumarinoxy) methane (0.2).	6	Acetic acid colourless crystals.	218	C ₃₁ H ₂₂ O ₆	75.68	75.91	4.44	4.52
5-Hydroxy-4,7-dimethyl coumarin (0.3).	bi(4,5-dimethyl-5-coumarinoxy) methane (0.1).	8	Acetic acid colourless crystals.	277	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₆	70.36	70.40	5.39	5.14

* All the melting points are uncorrected.

7. H. Suginome, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1960, 19, 16.

The general process for the synthesis of bi(coumarinoxy) methane derivatives: The hydroxycoumarin (0.02 *M*) was refluxed with dry acetone, methylene iodide (0.01 *M*) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.04 *M*) for the particular period depending upon the compound used. (See Table 1). Acetone was distilled off and water added to the residue. The solid after filtration was washed with dilute alkali and crystallised from acetic acid. The compound did not develop any ferric chloride colouration while the original hydroxy coumarin developed.

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Errata

Vol. 46, No. 2, page 182 line 8	For $\pi = \pi^*$ transition	Read $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition
Vol. 46, No. 3, page 268	Legends to Fig. 1	<p>— · — · — [MoO₂(o-tolyl)₂]</p> <p>———— [MoO₂(p-tolyl)₂]</p> <p>· · · · · [MoO₂(Benzoyl)₂]</p>